

*Evidence-Based Toxicology Manuscript Assessment Form***Editorial Triage of Non-RR Primary Studies**

Version 1.0.0 | 24 January 2023

Note for submitting authors: The overall EBT submission assessment process is concerned with the potential publishability of a Working Paper, i.e. the extent to which sufficient work has been done that the relevant community would consider it to be a unit of contribution to the scientific literature.

The first stage of assessment is Editorial Triage. The goal of this stage is to assess a Working Paper against a minimum set of standards relating to the utility, validity, and transparency of the work. The assessment includes checks on ethics, data availability, and other requirements relating to reuse of data generated by the study. The Editor may also comment on issues that it could be useful to address prior to peer-review.

Instructions for Editor: Please work through the triage questionnaire, then in the Summary Section provide a brief summary of the Working Paper, your overall impression of it in terms of compliance with the journal's expectations for manuscripts of its type, and answer the two questions in the table below.

Manuscript title	A general-purpose protocol for facilitating standards compliance when planning systematic reviews
Manuscript ID	TEBT-2023-0001 (232613986)
Handling Editor	Olwenn Martin
Editor ORCID	0000-0003-2724-7882

Triage ChecksQuick Links: [Objectives](#) | [Experiment](#) | [Analysis](#) | [Transparency](#) | [Ethics](#)

Domain	1. Objectives, context, and mode of research				
Level of Concern	<input type="checkbox"/> Critical	<input type="checkbox"/> Serious	<input type="checkbox"/> Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> Minor	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> None
Specific Issues	<input type="checkbox"/> Clarity about the knowledge goals or hypotheses of the research (e.g. PECO) <input type="checkbox"/> Justification for conducting the research (context, rationale) <input type="checkbox"/> Differentiation between research in confirmatory or exploratory mode				
Comments					

Quick Links: [Objectives](#) | [Experiment](#) | [Analysis](#) | [Transparency](#) | [Ethics](#)

Domain	2. Soundness and rigour of experimental approach
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Level of Concern	<input type="checkbox"/> Critical	<input type="checkbox"/> Serious	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> Minor	<input type="checkbox"/> None
Specific Issues	<input type="checkbox"/> Theory as to how the experiment delivers the knowledge goal <input type="checkbox"/> Identification and authentication of experimental components <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Sufficiency of power and replicates <input type="checkbox"/> Bias controls (e.g. randomisation, blinding, complete data, calibration & training)				
Comments	<p>Given the objective of the work is to explore whether developing the operational process for SR protocol development would improve compliance with conduct standards and checklists (i.e. build theoretical understanding), there are issues regarding the structure of the manuscript and to what extent the current methods and results sections are aligned with this objective. A key question to answer here is whether the use of a hypothetical example for a SR protocol to demonstrate the use of the tool would be considered sufficient or if a real case study is necessary prior to publication.</p>				

Quick Links: [Objectives](#) | [Experiment](#) | [Analysis](#) | [Transparency](#) | [Ethics](#)

Domain	3. Analysis of data and reporting of results				
Level of Concern	<input type="checkbox"/> Critical	<input type="checkbox"/> Serious	<input type="checkbox"/> Moderate	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Minor	<input type="checkbox"/> None
Specific Issues	<input type="checkbox"/> Data normalisation and cleansing techniques <input type="checkbox"/> Analysis pipeline (qualitative, narrative, and/or statistical methods) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Summarisation and visualisation of results <input type="checkbox"/> Selectivity in use of data or emphasis on study results				
Comments	<p>The structure of the manuscript is challenging. Whilst this is related to the topic and development of a tool, some material presented in discussion should be covered results (and potentially methods).</p>				

Quick Links: [Objectives](#) | [Experiment](#) | [Analysis](#) | [Transparency](#) | [Ethics](#)

Domain	4. Transparency and reproducibility				
Level of Concern	<input type="checkbox"/> Critical	<input type="checkbox"/> Serious	<input type="checkbox"/> Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> Minor	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> None
Specific Issues	<input type="checkbox"/> Citation of data, program code, and methods (TOP 1 - L3) <input type="checkbox"/> Provision of code, data, and materials for third-party replication (TOP 2,3,4 - L2) <input type="checkbox"/> Appropriateness and/or implementation of reporting checklist (TOP 5 - L3) <input type="checkbox"/> Description of and/or adherence to preregistered methods (TOP 6,7 - L1)				
Comments					

Quick Links: [Objectives](#) | [Experiment](#) | [Analysis](#) | [Transparency](#) | [Ethics](#)

Domain	5. Ethics and interests				
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Level of Concern	<input type="checkbox"/> Critical	<input type="checkbox"/> Serious	<input type="checkbox"/> Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> Minor	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> None
Specific Issues	<input type="checkbox"/> Informativeness of declarations of interests <input type="checkbox"/> Ethical approval for research with human or animal material or participants				
Comments					

Summary section

Summary of compliance issues

What is the impact of the compliance issues you have identified on the publishability of the Working Paper?	Do you agree that it is feasible to overcome the compliance issues?
<input type="checkbox"/> Critical <input type="checkbox"/> Serious <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Moderate <input type="checkbox"/> Minor <input type="checkbox"/> None	<input type="checkbox"/> Strongly disagree <input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat disagree <input type="checkbox"/> Neither agree nor disagree <input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat agree <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Strongly agree
Guidance note: Seriousness of the issue is independent of effort required to resolve it. For example, not meeting our requirements for citation standards (TOP 1, level 3) may not require much effort to resolve, but would be a critical issue. Critical and serious issues must be resolved prior to peer-review.	Guidance note: Feasibility is contextual, but in general issues that require additional experimental work or analysis of 3 or more months duration, and/or would result in the study being a different unit of contribution, is less feasible. This is a subjective judgement, provided to inform discussion of how to proceed with the Working Paper.

Summary of manuscript, your overall impression, and suggested course of action

This is an interesting manuscript; the development of the tool is important to the field and the work is undoubtedly worthy of publication. Potentially because it relates to the development of a tool, the logical structure of the manuscript is challenging. I would be interested in hearing reviewers' views and suggestions in terms of organisation of the materials and presentation of results, i.e. what belongs to methods, results and/or discussion, with specific reference to the stated objective and research hypothesis. Another important question for reviewers to answer would be whether running the tool for a hypothetical example is sufficient to demonstrate its the successful implementation.